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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

D1.3 – Data Governance and Intellectual Property Rights Handbook. v2

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Version - Status:	V1 – Final
Submission Date:	23/12/2025
Dissemination Level:	PUBLIC

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Report information

Purpose of the Report	This deliverable presents the updated Data Management Plan and Intellectual Property Rights framework for the iDriving project at Month 18. It reflects the project’s progress and experience gained during the first phase of implementation. The report supports compliant, secure, and efficient management of data and results throughout the project lifecycle.		
Relevant Work package:	WPI		
Relevant Task:	T1.4 & T1.5		
Contributors:	CERTH, SIMAVI		
Next version Title:	Data Governance and Intellectual Property Rights Handbook v.3	Next version Date:	30/06/2027
Official Submission Date:	31/12/2027	Actual Submission Date:	23/12/2025

ABOUT iDRIVING

iDriving, a 3-year Horizon-funded project, unites 17 European partners in a mission to enhance road safety. The project focuses on transforming urban and secondary rural road infrastructure through innovation. It aligns with the EU's goals for smart transport and actively embraces emerging technologies. Key areas of impact include enhancing driver behaviour, improving infrastructure safety, and empowering first responders. Through a comprehensive Safety Criteria Catalogue, innovative sensors, AI-based warnings, and a Digital Twin, iDriving paves the way for safer roads.

The iDriving consortium consists of the following partners:

No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	POLYTECHNEIO KRITIS	TUC	EL

3	AUSTRIATECH - GESELLSCHAFT DES BUNDES FÜR AT TECHNOLOGIEPOLITISCHE MASSNAHMEN GMBH	AUSTRIATECH	AT
4	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	UNI.EIFFEL	FR
5	FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	ES
6	INGARTEK CONSULTING SL	ING	ES
7	INFRA PLAN KONZALTNIG JDOO ZA USLUGE	INFRA PLAN	HR
8	ACCELIGENCE LTD	ACCELI	CY
9	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	INTRA	LU
10	SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL	SIMAVI	RO
11	ALP.Lab GmbH	ALP.LAB	AT
12	MUNICIPALITY OF ALBA IULIA	AIM	RO
13	DRAXIS RESEARCH VENTURES ASTIKI MI EL KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIRIA	DREVEN	EL
14	PRAVO I INTERNET FOUNDATION	LIF	BG
15	DIMOS THESSALONIKIS	THESSALONIKI	EL
16	GRAD KARLOVAC	COK	HR
17	MOBILYSIS SARL	MOBILYSIS SARL	CH

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Partner	Description
0.1	21.10.2025	Rada Stoilova	LIF	First version of ToC
0.2	25.10.2025	Alexandros Sfyridis	CERTH	Review of ToC
0.3	26.11.2025	Rada Stoilova	LIF	First draft
0.4	09.12.2025	Irina Stipanovic Eneko Elizondo	INFRA PLAN ING	Internal review
0.5	18.12.2025	Rada Stoilova	LIF	Comments addressed
0.4	21.12.2025	Alexandros Sfyridis	CERTH	Quality check
1.0	23.12.2025	Alexandros Sfyridis	CERTH	Submission to EC

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Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CC0	Creative Commons Zero
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Identifier of an Object
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JOA	Joint Ownership Agreement
RCD	Registered Community Design
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
UCD	Unregistered Community Design

Executive summary

This deliverable presents the updated Data Management Plan (DMP) and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) framework for the iDriving project as part of the M18 reporting cycle. Building on the foundation established in earlier iterations, this version provides an enhanced and more mature picture of data governance and intellectual property management across the consortium. It reflects the expanded data collection activities, the increased volume and diversity of datasets produced, and the progress in consolidating the project's IP assets as technical developments advance.

The DMP section synthesises comprehensive information provided by all consortium partners regarding the types, origin, and formats of data generated during the first 18 months. It evaluates the consortium's implementation of the FAIR principles, Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability, and documents improvements since the previous reporting cycle. Most partners have now formalised their internal procedures for naming, storing, and sharing data, and several have prepared or deposited datasets in trusted repositories. For sensitive data, including UAV imagery, personal data, and operational logs, enhanced security and access-control mechanisms have been implemented to ensure GDPR compliance.

The IPR section expands on the obligations under the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA), with a specific focus on the operationalisation of IP management as the project enters a more mature phase of development. At M18, several partners have identified tangible foreground results, and the updated IPR Registry documents these assets, their ownership, possible protection routes and access rights. This iteration places particular emphasis on joint results, internal exploitation planning, and the alignment of protection strategies with upcoming integration, validation, and demonstration activities.

1 Introduction

The present deliverable provides the updated Data Management Plan and Intellectual Property Rights framework for the iDriving project at Month 18 (M18). As the project advances from initial setup and early prototyping to more mature development and integration activities, the need for structured data governance and clear intellectual property management becomes increasingly important.

This document consolidates inputs from all consortium partners and reflects the practical experience gained during the first 18 months of data collection, technical development, and collaborative work. It outlines the procedures, responsibilities, and strategic considerations that guide the generation, handling, protection, and exploitation of data and results within the project. The updated DMP and IPR framework aim to ensure compliance with the GA, the CA, and relevant legal and ethical requirements, while supporting efficient cooperation and maximising the long-term value of the project's outputs.

1.1 Document Structure

This document is organised into three main parts:

- **Section 1 – Introduction:** Presents the context, purpose, and structure of the deliverable.
- **Section 2 – Data Management Plan:** Provides a detailed assessment of the project's data lifecycle management. It includes a summary of all datasets generated, adherence to the FAIR principles, procedures for ensuring data quality and security, and mechanisms for handling personal and sensitive information.
- **Section 3 – Intellectual Property:** Describes the requirements stemming from the GA and CA and outlines the project's approach to identifying, classifying, protecting, and managing foreground IP. It also details the current status of iDriving's IP assets and the strategies for managing joint results and future exploitation.

2 Data Management Plan

2.1 Data Summary

2.1.1 Overall infrastructure and obligations

iDriving is heavily dependent on data. Annex 1 – the DMP Questionnaire template, presents the main data collection tool that served as a source for the creation of this version of the DMP. The Questionnaire helped highlight how data is collected in relation to the project goals and how the main obligations relevant to data processing are implemented. The main infrastructure that was used for data collection and generation was the following:

- Digital twins
- Detection tools
- UAV/Cameras

It is important to mention that the report does not exclude other data processing activities which need to be covered and fall under various legal or other obligations.

2.1.2 Purpose of the Data

The data collected and generated serves a wide range of purposes integral to achieving the iDriving project's objectives. At a foundational level, data is used for technical validation, such as the logs collected by INTRA, which serve to validate communication between integrated systems, identify integration issues or errors, and understand partner system configurations. Similarly, TEKNIKER's Interoperability and Shareability Data is necessary for all iDriving systems to share information and communicate in a standardized way, ensuring seamless collaboration.

A primary focus across multiple partners as this is relevant for the project goals is the enhancement of road safety, monitoring, and infrastructure management. INFRAPLAN will use its data to monitor road safety, assess infrastructure conditions, optimize maintenance schedules, and improve traffic flow. This is complemented by data from Université Gustave Eiffel, which is used to monitor infrastructure sharing among diverse users (e.g., vehicles, bicycles, pedestrians), infer safety indicators, analyse congestion patterns, and optimize infrastructure via predictive models. Similarly, CERTH's data collection aims to improve AI models, optimize maintenance operations, enhance situational awareness for tasks like UAV path planning, and contribute to building a Digital Twin of the road infrastructure.

Data also serves as the direct input for developing and testing specific project tools and methodologies. TEKNIKER will use technical information to feed and train data-driven models for anomaly detection and predictive maintenance algorithms, and its analytical data will form the foundation for generating an alert system for end users. While MobiLysis will use aggregated traffic and incident data as input

for its traffic management tools (route guidance and signal control) within a simulation environment, allowing for the testing of safety and efficiency objectives. The technical data produced by TUC from simulations is specifically intended for the evaluation of methodologies developed in project tasks T3.2 and T5.3. Similarly relevant to the goal of research and development INGARTEK will use the collected technical data to contribute for the development of relevant standards and standardisation processes.

Specialized data is collected for specific operational goals. DREVEN's data, for example, will provide current weather conditions, generate high-resolution data to enhance accuracy, and be used to develop AI-generated meteorological warnings to improve forecasting. ACCELIGENCE's drone data serves to detect incidents, provide real-time intelligence for decision-making, and ensure reliable communication for drone missions.

Finally, data collection supports specific use cases and project dissemination. The data collected by THESSALONIKI is intended to support the successful implementation of the Thessaloniki Use Case (T2.3). Separately, ACCELIGENCE's dissemination data (e.g., website analytics) serves to establish a brand identity, track communication effectiveness, and inform stakeholders. INGARTEK data processing activities will support the research of market development and analysis of stakeholder interactions.

2.1.3 Data Types

The iDriving project involves a consortium of partners collecting, generating, and administering various types of data for the needs of the project objectives. The purpose of this section of D1.3 is to consolidate information about types of data collected and processed within the project activities. The information will guide the consortium on handling data throughout the project's lifetime and support strategic decisions regarding the project's results.

The data collected and generated for the iDriving project is highly diverse, sourced from a combination of real-world sensors, simulations, and internal systems. The data types fall into several key categories:

- Technical and Operational data;
- Data collected from real time sensors (Sensor Data);
- Environmental Data;
- Analytical and Generated Data;
- Dissemination Data (that could be shared for the project purposes).

A critical aspect of the project is the governance of personal data processing activities. While several partners have collected personal data (license plates, videos of pedestrian behaviour) measures like pseudonymisation and anonymisation will ensure that compliance with GDPR is guaranteed. This will be elaborated further in

section 2.4 of this deliverable. More information on the specific data types in the table below (Table 1):

Table 1 - Data Type Collected within iDriving

Partner organisation	Data Type collected within iDriving
ACCELIGENCE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensor data (RGB Images / Videos) collected by drones • Data that will be processed by AI algorithms • Communication and telemetry data from the UAV systems • Visual identity assets (e.g., logos, banners, e-newsletters, promotional material) • Website and social media analytics data (traffic, engagement metrics) • News articles and updates, scientific publications and press releases shared on the iDriving website
CERTH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual data: High-resolution images and videos • Telemetry data: Includes GPS coordinates, altitude, speed, and other flight parameters from UAVs for mission planning and execution. • Object detection and classification results: Outputs from deep learning models identifying vehicles, pedestrians, road signs, and other relevant objects in real-time. • UAV path plans: AI-generated flight paths and schedules for UAVs, optimized based on area size and resource availability. • 3D radiance field data: Data describing 3D objects that were created by using 2D images • Defect quantification metrics: Measurements of road defects to prioritize maintenance activities.
DREVEN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raw data, text, numerical data, code, and maps.
INFRAPLAN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videos, images, traffic data (may contain personal data – including pseudonymised data).
INTRA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logs generated from system interactions between partners. • Operational data and possibly metadata about the systems involved in the integration process.
INGARTEK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contact information • Standardization processes, • Market status, • Stakeholder interactions, • Competition analysis, • Business model frameworks.
MobiLysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregated, anonymized travel demand information

TEKNIKER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GPS location data for drivers and road users, user-provided information on road conditions or behavioural data related to driving patterns (personal data) • Open Source data – in dataset • Traffic flow, road conditions, environmental factors, and operational details from UAV path planning and resource allocation.
THESSALONIKI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Data, Air Pollution Data, Meteorological Data, Traffic Data.
TUC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical data (simulations)
Université Eiffel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Video data: Data from UAVs and ground cameras (video feeds) capturing traffic, road user trajectory and safety incidents. • Traffic data, including vehicle speeds, congestion levels, and flow rates, is provided by the use case leaders to train and develop iDriving tasks. • Safety assessment Data: Road user behaviour data, such as lane violations, zebra crossing compliance, and use of hand signals by bicyclists, extracted from camera and UAV feeds.
AustriaTech	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey data: • Technical evaluation data: • Contact data (project partners information)

2.1.4 Data Formats and Size

The iDriving project will handle a wide array of data formats, reflecting the diversity of data sources. The data formats used in the project are largely standard, machine-readable formats, with JSON, CSV, and XML being the most common for structured data, and standard video/image formats (MP4, JPEG, PNG) used for visual data. Specialized formats like PLY (for 3D data) and .nc/.grib (for meteorological data) will be used where necessary.

Within the data processing activities under the project, the expected data sizes vary significantly, from megabyte-scale analytics to gigabyte-scale sensor logs and simulation outputs. The largest specified dataset is the video data from Université Eiffel, which is expected to reach approximately 1 TB, highlighting the significant storage and processing requirements for systems handling high-resolution visual data. Detailed description of the used data formats and indicative data size could be found in the table below (Table 2):

Table 2 - Data Formats

Partner organisation	Data Format
ACCELIGENCE	JSON or XML, CSV and HTML
CERTH	JPEG, PNG, TIFF, MP4, AV. 3D Radiance Field: PLY
DREVEN	nc, .txt, .csv, grib, pdf, .tiff
INFRAPLAN	video files, sensor logs, and image data formats
INTRA	JSON, CSV or XML
INGARTEK	text files and CSVs
MobiLysis	SUMO format for trips/routes files
TEKNIKER	csv, json or .mpeg-4
THESSALONIKI	csv, excel, pdf, image formats
TUC	ply/text files – ASCII format
Université Eiffel	MP4, CSV, JSON, GeoJSON
AustriaTech	CSV

2.2 FAIR Data

As stated in the previous version of the Data Governance and Intellectual property Handbook (D1.2) the main objective of the FAIR data concept is to give data greater value, considering enhanced reusability for future projects and research. Therefore, data should be easily discoverable, accessible, assessable, and intelligible, usable beyond the original purpose for which it was collected and wherever possible, interoperable to specific quality standards. The concept of the holistic and systemic approach considers that data should be as open as possible to increase the scientific and social value but also needs to be restricted when needed.

This section of the deliverable will present how the project partners are ensuring compliance with the FAIR principles up until the M18 of the project lifetime.

2.2.1 Findable Data

The "Findable" principle of FAIR data is the foundation for data reusability, ensuring that data and metadata can be easily discovered by both humans and computer systems. This is primarily achieved through unique identifiers (like DOIs), rich metadata, clear naming conventions, version control, and by making metadata indexable. The partners' approaches to findability vary in their level of detail and implementation, often reflecting the type of data they handle.

Several partners demonstrate a comprehensive strategy to make their data findable. Université Eiffel will assign a unique project identifier (iDriving-NEVERS-2025) and plans to assign DOIs to final, published datasets through repositories like

Zenodo (or Dataverse). They will use structured naming conventions, clear version numbers, keywords, and will make metadata available in machine-readable (XML, JSON) formats to be indexed. DREVEN also plans to use DOIs by depositing data in Zenodo, following its guidelines for identifiers, keywords, and harvestable metadata. Similarly, AustriaTech will include unique data identifiers. For publications in papers, the partners mentioned above are going to use DOI identifiers. Metadata includes source, date, format, and version, following project guidelines. ACCELIGENCE will use unique mission IDs for drone data and a project ID for dissemination materials, along with structured naming conventions, versioning, and keywords. Their website metadata is specifically designed to be harvested and indexed. CERTH will use unique IDs for data streams, provide version numbers, and use standards like EXIF and COCO JSON for its metadata.

Other partners have detailed internal findability measures but will restrict public discovery. TEKNIKER will assign persistent unique identifiers (UUIDs) for internal traceability and use a structured naming convention and versioning. However, they explicitly state their metadata will not be offered for harvesting. Similarly, INTRA will use system-generated IDs for its logs and a clear naming convention, but notes that keywords are "not relevant for logs" and its metadata is "not designed for public indexing".

A third group has a more basic implementation. INFRAPLAN will use date, time, and type as identifiers and follow standard naming conventions. Due to the sensitive nature of its surveillance data, it will *not* provide keywords or make its metadata harvestable. INGARTEK will follow the ISO 9001 standard as file naming convention. While THESSALONIKI for the same purpose will use "i.e., iDriving-THESS_Report_#.pdf" to track versions and maintain consistency and will provide version numbers, but states "No standards available" for DOIs and "Not applicable" for keywords and harvesting.

Finally, some partners have not yet finalized their findability strategy. MobilLysis reported that its approach to identifiers, standards, naming, versioning, keywords, and metadata is "Not yet finalized" or "Not yet defined". TUC has defined a clear naming convention, but there is not certainty, regarding versioning, keywords and metadata.

In conclusion the consortium's approach to compliance with the making data findable principle varies significantly. Partners like Université Eiffel, DREVEN, and ACCELIGENCE, who handle data intended for public or academic use, show the strongest alignment with the "Findable" principle. In contrast, partners handling sensitive operational data (like INFRAPLAN) or internal system data (like INTRA and TEKNIKER) are implementing more restricted, internal-facing findability measures. Other partners have not yet finalized their strategies.

2.2.2 Accessible Data

The “Accessible” principle of the FAIR Guidelines means that data and metadata should be retrievable by both humans and machines, using standardised protocols, and should be stored in a trusted repository. It doesn't always require open access; if data is sensitive, its metadata can be publicly available with clear conditions on how the data can be accessed, ensuring long-term preservation and enabling secure, controlled access.¹ Within the iDriving project, the consortium partners have adopted varied accessibility strategies tailored to the sensitivity of their data. While dissemination materials and aggregated research results are generally planned for open access via trusted repositories, raw operational data, particularly that involving personal identifiers or proprietary technology, will be subject to strict access controls to comply with GDPR and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and will be topic of section 2.4 and section 3 of this deliverable.

Under the project ACCELIGENCE distinguishes clearly between operational and dissemination data. Only anonymized or non-sensitive processed data will be made available for public sharing, primarily deposited in general-purpose repositories like Zenodo. Conversely, raw drone data containing sensitive information will be restricted to authorized users within the consortium to maintain privacy and security. All communication materials will be accessible via the iDriving website, and metadata will be openly available under a CC0 license to facilitate discovery.

AustriaTech and INGRATEK are also implementing similar dual strategy. Project publications, reports, and non-sensitive documentation will be accessible through secure, trusted repositories such as Zenodo, the EU Open Research Repository, and the project website. Raw data used for deliverables may be made public if it is deemed of public interest. For internal consortium use, non-public data will be stored on Microsoft SharePoint. A specific accessibility note regarding C-ITS data highlights that while .pcap files can be accessed with free tools, .blf files require the Vector CANoe tool, which necessitates a paid license.

DREVEN intends to make data publicly available through the iDriving platform. While the weather forecasting process relies on open-source data, DREVEN's proprietary forecasting methodology and code will be available only upon request. If released, data will be accessible via Zenodo, Git, or Docker Hub. However, data stored on internal platforms like SharePoint will remain restricted to authorized users for security reasons. Université Gustave Eiffel plans to make aggregated traffic patterns, road user behaviour trends, and simulation results available openly. Data will be deposited in trusted repositories like Zenodo or Dataverse and accessible through the iDriving portal. Strict restrictions will apply to data containing identifiable road user information (due to GDPR) and data from vehicle

¹ [Research Data Management Support, The FAIR Principles, University of Utrecht](#)

manufacturers (due to contracts). Metadata will likely be made available under a CCO license.

Apart from this dual approach several partners are implementing a control-based access to data, where the requested information is provided, but requires additional oversight. For example, MobiLysis plans to share data produced by scenario simulations with iDriving partners upon request using OneDrive. All used and produced data will be stored on encrypted, password-protected hard drives, while code will be deposited in iDriving GitHub repositories. TUC plans to make parts of the data produced within specific tasks (T3.2 and T5.3) available. This data will be deposited in TUC's OneDrive repository. Access will initially be restricted to project partners upon request, with identity verification conducted through email communication. Finally, considering the types of data that they will be collecting and processing during the project lifetime THESSALONIKI will consult with their DPO regarding the release of data. Project publications and non-sensitive documentation will be made openly available provided there are no legal restrictions. Internal data will be stored on Microsoft SharePoint.

The third group is related to restricted and technical data handling procedures for partners dealing with highly sensitive or purely technical data where accessibility is more tightly constrained. In this group INTRA, which handles sensitive system logs, does not plan to make data openly available at this stage; access is confined to project partners for integration purposes via internal infrastructure. Data will primarily be accessible internally to project partners through a shared platform or internal cloud infrastructure. INFRAPLAN determines availability on a case-by-case basis, strictly limiting access to personal or identifiable data to prevent misuse. TEKNIKER adopts a nuanced approach based on data type: while their generated analytical data remains restricted to the consortium, they plan to make their Interoperability and Shareability data (ontologies) openly available to the community in OWL format.

In conclusion within the iDriving consortium demonstrates a robust compliance with the "Accessible" principle through a multi-layered approach. Trusted public resources like Zenodo are favoured for sharing non-sensitive research findings, ensuring long-term accessibility for the scientific community. However, for operational and sensitive data, partners prioritize security by utilizing restricted platforms (SharePoint, OneDrive, internal clouds) and implementing clear authentication protocols (such as request forms and identity verification). This balanced approach ensures that while valuable research is disseminated, the privacy of individuals and the intellectual property of partners remain protected.

2.2.3 Interoperable Data

The "Interoperable" principle ensures that data will use standardized formats, shared vocabularies, and formal, accessible language so it can be integrated and exchanged between different computer systems, applications and workflows

without special effort. ² iDriving will follow metadata standards for general data documentation. This will ensure compatibility with other datasets and systems, facilitating easier data sharing and integration. For example, with web analytics data, Google Analytics metadata standards will be followed. Within the iDriving project, the consortium partners have adopted a range of strategies to ensure their data can be exchanged and interpreted across different systems, balancing the use of established international standards with project-specific internal protocols.

A significant number of partners are aligning with well-recognized external standards to maximize compatibility. Université Gustave Eiffel employs a robust framework, utilizing Dublin Core for general metadata, ISO 19115 for geospatial data, and IEEE standards for traffic data. They also leverage specific vocabularies like DATEX II for real-time traffic information and GeoJSON for geospatial datasets. DREVEN adheres to the Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Conventions for their meteorological data, ensuring their NetCDF outputs are structured and self-describing for the scientific community. ACCELIGENCE also commits to established metadata standards for general documentation and geospatial data (ISO/OGC), ensuring their sensor and incident detection data remains compatible with external systems. INGARTEK is using standard vocabularies to enhance the clarity and interoperability of their data outputs. Additionally they will follow the Dublin Core Metadata Standards to provide clear and consistent framework.

Some partners are focusing on internal consistency or are developing specific models for the project's unique needs. CERTH plans to design and develop a unified data model to support various data types rather than following a single pre-existing vocabulary standard. INTRA, dealing with system logs, will rely on internal standards for log formatting and metadata tagging (e.g., system IDs, timestamps) rather than external vocabularies, ensuring consistency within the project's internal infrastructure. TEKNIKER and INFRAPLAN have indicated that while they will follow methodologies to facilitate interoperability, the specific standards are still to be determined or finalized during the project.

A strong consensus exists across the consortium regarding the format of the data. Almost all partners—including ACCELIGENCE, CERTH, DREVEN, INTRA, TEKNIKER, TUC, and Université Gustave Eiffel—have confirmed that data will be made available in standard, machine-readable formats such as CSV, JSON, XML, and GeoJSON. This ensures that the data generated can be easily ingested, processed, and reused by other software tools and researchers. MobiLysis and THESSALONIKI are still in the process of defining their final formats, noting that this will depend on the specific availability and type of data collected as the project progresses.

To further enhance interoperability, several partners have committed to openly publishing any new vocabularies or ontologies created during the project.

² [Making Data FAIR, Australian Research Data Commons](#)

Université Gustave Eiffel, TEKNIKER, and TUC explicitly state that if project-specific vocabularies are developed, they will be shared openly (e.g., under a Creative Commons license) to allow for reuse and extension by the community. Conversely, INTRA notes that any project-specific vocabulary created for their internal logs would likely remain confidential due to the nature of their data.

In conclusion the iDriving consortium is taking a proactive approach to interoperability, with a clear preference for established international standards (ISO, Dublin Core, CF) and machine-readable formats (JSON, CSV) among the technical and research partners. While some specific standards remain to be defined by partners like INFRAPLAN and MobiLysis, the overall strategy is well-aligned to ensure that data can be effectively integrated and reused both within the consortium and by the broader scientific and industrial community.

2.2.4 Reusable Data

The "Reusable" principle of the FAIR guidelines ensures that data assets are richly described, released with a clear data usage license, and ready for future research and analysis. Within this principle, data must be understandable and usable for a wide range of contexts by ensuring it is well-described with rich, human and Machine-readable metadata and clear licensing. This included detailed contextual information, clear usage licenses, and described provenance so users can understand the data origin and assess its suitability for their needs, ultimately optimizing its reuse for new research.³

Within the iDriving project, the consortium partners have generally committed to making non-sensitive data available for reuse by the broader scientific and industrial community. This commitment is supported by plans for comprehensive documentation and specific licensing frameworks, although strict restrictions remain for data involving personal identifiers or proprietary technology.

Several partners have outlined robust strategies to maximize data reuse through standard licensing and documentation with the adoption of the relevant open standards. Université Gustave Eiffel and TEKNIKER plan to license their data under Creative Commons (CC BY 4.0 and CC BY-NC 4.0, respectively), ensuring that users can share and adapt the material with appropriate attribution. ACCELIGENCE, INGARTEK and INFRAPLAN also intend to use open licenses like CC-BY or the public domain dedication CC0 for their non-sensitive datasets. DREVEN also aligns with this approach, aiming to apply open licenses where possible and adhere to Horizon Europe guidelines for a five-year retention period. To facilitate actual reuse, these partners, along with CERTH, have committed to providing essential documentation, including README files, codebooks, methodology descriptions, and even Jupyter Notebooks to validate data analysis.

³ [FAIR data principles, Research Data Management – KU Leuven](#)

The iDriving consortium has identified key groups likely to benefit from reusing iDriving data, including academic researchers, traffic management agencies, urban planners, and smart city developers. AustriaTech notes interest from policymakers and experts in Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM). Regarding timing, most partners plan to make data available either immediately after processing or following the project's completion. Université Gustave Eiffel notes a potential embargo period of up to one year for sensitive data, while CERTH and AustriaTech confirm data will remain reusable for at least five years post-project.

Not all data will be available for public reuse. INTRA, handling sensitive system logs, has explicitly stated that reuse will be strictly limited to project partners for troubleshooting and integrating purposes, with no plans for public domain release. Similarly, INFRAPLAN, INGARTEK and TEKNIER emphasize that sensitive or personal data will be restricted to project confidentiality and comply with GDPR. MobiLysis, TUC and THESSALONIKI are currently in a have not yet determined a clear strategy for compliance with the Reusable principle.

The iDriving consortium demonstrates a clear intent to support the Reusable principle for non-sensitive research data. By adopting standard licenses (Creative Commons) and committing to rich documentation (methodologies, codebooks), the project partners are setting a strong foundation for future research utility. However, the strategy remains flexible, as data security and privacy are prioritized where operational sensitivity dictates restricted access.

2.2.5 Allocation of Resources

In order to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project, all project partners we asked to provide estimation what resources would be required to ensure proper data management during the project. This section of the deliverable outlines how the iDriving consortium plans to sustain data management activities through the project lifecycle. This includes defining the financial, human and technical assets to ensure data is secure, accessible and compliant with the FAIR principles. Across the consortium, there is a general consensus that data management is an integral part of the project's budget, though the specific allocation strategies vary depending on the partner's role and the volume of data they handle.

Most partners have dedicated significant human and technical resources to data management. ACCELIGENCE, DREVEN, and TEKNIKER have appointed multidisciplinary teams comprising data scientists, IT specialists, and project coordinators. These teams are supported by robust technical infrastructure, including cloud storage, encrypted servers, and specialized software for data assimilation (e.g., WRF models for DREVEN). AustriaTech and Université Gustave Eiffel rely heavily on established internal support structures, utilizing their organization's Data Protection Officers (DPOs) and IT support levels to manage on-

premise and cloud storage (SharePoint). INTRA also allocates specific human resources for data management and IT, ensuring secure cloud infrastructure and tools are available for handling system logs. CERTH, TUC, and INFRAPLAN have allocated general financial and human resources to handle data processing and equipment needs.

The consortium is divided regarding the additional costs required to make data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Partners dealing with complex or large-scale data, specifically ACCELIGENCE, INFRAPLAN, INTRA, and Université Gustave Eiffel, anticipate extra costs. These include expenses for data formatting, metadata creation, cloud storage fees, and potential repository charges, all of which are covered by the allocated project budget. Université Gustave Eiffel and INTRA also note the potential need for specialist fees to maintain repositories or ensuring secure access. Conversely, AustriaTech, CERTH, TEKNIKER, TUC, INGARTEK and DREVEN do not foresee significant extra costs at this stage, planning to absorb data management activities within their existing overheads, internal IT budgets, or current service agreements.

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The iDriving consortium has proactively allocated resources to ensure robust data management. While partners with heavy data processing requirements (like TEKNIKER and Université Gustave Eiffel) have planned for significant time and financial investment, the overall strategy relies on a mix of project-allocated budgets and existing institutional infrastructure. This ensures that the necessary personnel, technology, and funding are in place to maintain data integrity and compliance throughout the project.

2.3 Data Quality

The activities related to the collection of information with the iDriving Data Management Plan Questionnaire from the relevant project partners did not cover a specific part related to Data Quality. Nevertheless, as mentioned in the previous version of this deliverable Data Quality is a requirement included in various legal

acts (most important is the AI Act⁴) thus making it highly important for the iDriving project goals. In relation to that, the consortium partners address data quality implicitly through various mechanisms as quality assurance is treated as an integral part of the data lifecycle, ensuring that data is accurate, consistent and reliable.

For example, partners involved in physical data collection emphasize the importance of hardware accuracy. CERTH explicitly states that all sensors and devices, including UAVs and cameras, are calibrated using standardized methods to ensure the accuracy of the visual and telemetry data collected. Similarly, Université Gustave Eiffel relies on documented data collection protocols to ensure that the generation process is reproducible and consistent across different trial sessions. TEKNIKER follows defined workflows that include specific stages for "data cleaning" and transformation to maintain quality before analysis begins.

For partners generating analytical or simulation data, quality is closely related with validation. INFRAPLAN notes that re-used data will be used to validate models and benchmark new results, ensuring that they are verified. DREVEN uses collected weather data specifically to initialize and validate its predictive models (WRF), ensuring the accuracy of the AI-generated alerts. INTRA uses its collected logs as a primary tool for validation, using them to identify integration errors and verify that system-to-system communications are functioning correctly.

Another primary method for ensuring data quality across the consortium is the provision of documentation that allows others (researchers, technology experts, policy maker etc.) to verify findings. ACCELIGENCE, TUC, TEKNIKER, INGARTEK and AustriaTech all commit to providing documentation (such as methodologies, codebooks, and README files) necessary to validate data analysis. MobiLysis plans to facilitate this validation through rich metadata accompanying their datasets. AustriaTech emphasizes that clear documentation of how survey data was collected and processed is essential for understanding the data's context and quality.

Another topic related to Data Quality is related to the allocation of resources, as stated by several partners quality requires effort. ACCELIGENCE explicitly allocates human resources for "quality checks" to ensure data meets FAIR principles. Université Gustave Eiffel estimates that 15-20% of their data management team's time will be dedicated to tasks that improve quality, such as data cleaning and

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act)

documentation. TEKNIKER also anticipates significant time investment for data curation and cleaning to ensure the analytical data is robust.

In conclusion the consortium ensures quality through a combination of technical calibration (for sensors), methodological validation (for AI and simulations), and transparent documentation (for reusability). By integrating quality checks into the data generation and resource allocation phases, the partners aim to produce datasets that are not only available but trustworthy and fit for purpose.

2.4 Data Security and Personal Data Protection

2.4.1 iDriving Personal Data Protection Approach

2.4.1.1 Personal Data within iDriving

All partners within the iDriving consortium process basic administrative personal data, specifically the personal data of project partners and employees, such as names, professional contact details and roles within the consortium, for internal coordination and communication. This processing is routine, limited and carried out in compliance with GDPR and institutional policies.

Except for this administrative data, several partners collect the personal data of external stakeholders, mainly contact information or professional identifiers, when conducting surveys, interviews, workshops or expert consultations required for specific project tasks. Such data is collected with appropriate consent and used solely for the purposes of the relevant research activities.

Further personal data is processed by a subset of partners as part of road-user-related research. Université Gustave Eiffel processes behavioural and location information derived from UAV and ground-camera recordings, including movement trajectories, traffic-rule compliance and incident-related contextual data. Tekniker collects GPS location data and user-provided information related to driving patterns and road conditions. ACCELIGENCE may process personal data captured incidentally through drone surveillance or incident-detection video, and may also collect IP addresses through web analytics. Alp.Lab records sample video streams within private premises to analyse helmet and seatbelt use for tool validation. CERTH may collect limited personal data for controlled demonstrations, including faces and licence plates. Infraplan may incidentally record identifiable elements such as licence plates or pedestrians in video material.

In terms of data concerning criminal convictions and offences, operational data for law enforcement agencies, sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection, classified information on national or international grounds, or commercially confidential information, the iDriving project does not collect, generate, or process any such data. The project focuses exclusively on road-user behaviour, traffic-related datasets, environmental and meteorological data, and administrative personal data for project coordination, and does not involve any of

the sensitive or classified categories listed above. All data processing is carried out within the European Union, and no personal or project-related data is transferred outside the EU.

Additionally, no personal data from children or vulnerable groups will be intentionally collected or processed. The project does not target minors or other vulnerable populations. Should public data collection activities (e.g., road-use observations) take place, vulnerable individuals may be present incidentally among the general public. To protect privacy and comply with GDPR, the project implements:

- Data minimisation, ensuring only strictly necessary data is collected;
- Anonymisation or pseudonymisation where appropriate;
- Technical and organisational measures to prevent re-identification of individuals.
- Any personal data that could fall under GDPR Article 9 (special categories of personal data) will be treated with special care in accordance with GDPR Articles 9 and 32, implementing appropriate technical and organisational safeguards to ensure confidentiality, integrity, and security.

2.4.1.2 Compliance with GDPR

All personal data processing within the iDriving project is conducted in full accordance with the GDPR and relevant national legislation. Partners adhere to the GDPR principles of lawfulness, fairness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimisation; accuracy; storage limitation; integrity and confidentiality; and accountability.

Whenever personal data is collected directly from individuals, such as stakeholders participating in interviews, surveys or expert consultations, or participants involved in controlled testing activities, explicit and informed consent is obtained prior to data collection. Participants are informed of the purpose of the processing, the legal basis, the retention period, the types of data collected, and their data protection rights, including access, rectification, erasure, objection and data portability.

For processing activities involving video, UAV footage or other forms of behavioural monitoring, partners will ensure appropriate transparency measures. These include visible notifications in areas where cameras or drones operate, clearly informing individuals that data is being recorded and directing them to further information regarding their rights and contact points for additional inquiries. However, up to this point of the project, pilots are planned to take in a controlled environment. In these scenarios, all participants are informed about the nature of the testing and provide explicit consent prior to participation. No data is collected from members of the public in uncontrolled settings without appropriate notification, safeguards and compliance checks.

Data minimisation is strictly applied across all processing operations. Only the data necessary to fulfil the defined research objectives is collected, and personal identifiers are avoided wherever possible. When identifiable information is included in the raw dataset, such as faces, licence plates or potentially identifiable road-user trajectories, partners apply measures such as anonymisation, aggregation or pseudonymisation at the earliest technically feasible stage. Techniques include face and license plate blurring, removal of direct identifiers and secure separation of identifying information from research datasets.

Data retention follows the principle of storage limitation. Personal data is retained only for as long as necessary to complete the relevant research or administrative task and is subsequently anonymised or securely deleted in accordance with institutional policies and the project's data management plan. Retention periods for consent-based data collection are communicated to participants during the consent process.

Where processing activities involve higher risk, such as large-scale behavioural analysis through video analytics or the use of drones, partners will conduct a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) to identify and mitigate risks to data subjects. Ethical approval from national or institutional Data Protection Officers (DPOs) or ethics committees is obtained where required.

Additional technical and organisational measures safeguard the confidentiality, integrity and availability of personal data. These include secure storage environments, encryption of data in transit and at rest, access control mechanisms, authentication measures, audit logs, and the separation of personal data from operational and analytical datasets. Access to personal data is restricted to authorised personnel only, based on the principle of least privilege.

2.4.2 iDriving Data Security Approach

The iDriving project follows a secure-by-design and secure-by-default approach that complies with GDPR security requirements, Horizon Europe requirements, and internationally recognised information security principles such as those defined in ISO/IEC 27001. The data security framework continues to be grounded in the principles of confidentiality, integrity and availability, ensuring that all data is protected during collection, processing, storage, sharing and long-term preservation. In this second iteration of the Data Management Plan, the consortium has refined its security model to reflect updated workflows, the expansion of research datasets, and the integration of new software components.

The iDriving consortium has identified several key security risks affecting both administrative and research datasets, including unauthorised access, data breaches or cyberattacks, accidental or intentional data leakage, and data loss or corruption. These datasets include project documents, UAV and camera footage, and web-based tools. Additional partner-specific threats include phishing, data loss during transmission of incident-detection data, and vulnerabilities in web analytics or communication platforms.

To address these risks, partners conduct ongoing risk assessments to identify and evaluate potential threats, including infrastructure failures and vulnerabilities in cloud services or external platforms. These assessments inform the selection, implementation, and continuous update of technical, organisational, and procedural safeguards. Threat modelling is revisited regularly to ensure that new system components are incorporated into the security framework, and access rights, infrastructure configurations, and control mechanisms are reviewed and updated as necessary. This continuous assessment process ensures that risks are proactively managed and that the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of project data are maintained.

2.4.2.1 Technical Security Measures

A common set of minimum technical requirements guides partners in protecting project data. These include encryption of data at rest and in transit (e.g., AES-256, TLS/HTTPS), strong authentication, role-based access, secure remote access, and the use of maintained audit logs. Institutional IT environments apply measures such as firewalls, network segmentation, vulnerability scanning, antivirus protection and regular software patching. Cloud and collaborative platforms (e.g., institutional servers, Microsoft 365, secure research repositories) are selected based on their compliance with GDPR and their ability to provide encrypted storage, controlled sharing functions and continuous monitoring.

2.4.2.2 Backup, Recovery and Business Continuity

Data availability is ensured through partner-level backup and recovery strategies. Backups are performed regularly and stored in secure cloud environments or physically separate institutional locations. Redundancy mechanisms, including RAID and mirrored systems, reduce the risk of data loss. Recovery procedures are periodically tested to confirm that essential data can be restored efficiently and that project activities can continue without disruption.

2.4.2.3 Incident Detection, Response and Reporting

Security incidents are managed through local incident response procedures aligned with consortium guidelines. Systems are monitored for irregular activity, and logs of user actions, data modifications, and system events support early detection and investigation. When incidents occur, containment, diagnostics, and remediation are initiated immediately. Each partner is responsible for managing incidents affecting its own systems and for complying with applicable legal obligations, including GDPR for personal data, cybersecurity requirements informed by the NIS2 Directive, and, where relevant, requirements under the AI Act for AI-based components of the project.

For personal data, any breaches are handled in accordance with GDPR Articles 33 and 34, including notification to supervisory authorities and, where appropriate, affected individuals. Risk assessments are conducted to determine the nature of the breach, the affected data subjects, and the potential consequences. Documentation of incidents includes the facts of the breach, its effects, and remedial actions taken, enabling verification of compliance and supporting continuous improvement.

For non-personal data, system-level incidents, and data generated or processed by AI components, incident detection and response are informed by NIS2 principles.² This includes continuous monitoring for anomalous activity, early detection and classification of incidents, mitigation of impacts on essential project services, and consideration of cascading effects arising from dependencies on third-party or cloud service providers. When incidents occur, partners promptly carry out containment, diagnostics, and remediation. Audit logs, system monitoring, and access records support incident investigation and continuous improvement. Corrective actions and lessons learned are documented and shared across the consortium to strengthen overall security and resilience.

2.4.2.4 Retention, Deletion and Long-Term Preservation

Data retention policies follow Horizon Europe guidelines, which typically require that data be maintained for at least five years after the conclusion of the project. Certain categories of research outputs may be preserved for longer periods to support scientific reuse and transparency. Personal data is processed according to the principles of data minimisation and storage limitation and is deleted once it is no longer necessary. Secure deletion methods are applied to ensure that removed data cannot be reconstructed. Long-term preservation relies on trusted institutional repositories, certified cloud services or recognised open-access platforms that guarantee ongoing security and accessibility.

2.4.2.5 Use of External Services and Third-Party Platforms

The project uses several third-party platforms for cloud storage, software development, data exchange, and documentation management. Partners ensure that external service providers comply with GDPR requirements for personal data and apply security measures for non-personal data and system-level services in line with NIS2 principles. This includes evaluating the security of suppliers, cloud services, and other dependencies, implementing proportionate technical, organisational, and procedural safeguards, and monitoring the adequacy of their incident response and continuity capabilities. Platforms are selected based on their adherence to industry-standard security practices, including encryption, access control, and clear data handling policies.

3 Intellectual Property

This section provides the updated IP framework for the iDriving project at M18. While the first iteration of this deliverable primarily described the main forms of IP protection to be considered, the present version goes beyond listing protection mechanisms. It focuses on clarifying and operationalising the iDriving IPR Management Strategy, reflecting the project's progression toward more advanced technical development, integration, and exploitation activities.

The collaborative nature of iDriving requires a transparent and structured approach to the identification, protection, sharing, and use of intellectual assets generated within the consortium. This includes ensuring compliance with the obligations defined in the GA and CA, establishing clear ownership rules, and enabling appropriate access rights to support both project implementation and long-term exploitation.

3.1 Requirements as per the GA and CA

3.1.1 Ownership and Transfer of Results

Under the provisions of the Grant Agreement (Annex 5, Article 16) and the Consortium Agreement, ownership of project results follows the principle of origin. Each partner remains the sole owner of the results it generates and retains all associated economic rights, including the right to apply for and maintain intellectual property protection.

Given the collaborative implementation of iDriving, certain outputs may be created through the combined contributions of multiple partners. Where this occurs, the resulting asset is subject to joint ownership by the contributing partners. In such cases, the joint owners are required to formalise the governance of the result through a written Joint Ownership Agreement, which establishes how the asset may be used, protected, and exploited.

Unless otherwise agreed in writing, each joint owner may independently use jointly owned results for non-commercial research and educational purposes without financial compensation and without seeking prior approval from the other owners. Such permitted uses are limited to academic, training, and internal scientific activities. They explicitly exclude commercial exploitation, contract research, revenue-generating services, product development, or standardisation activities. Participation in further collaborative research projects is allowed, provided that no commercial rights are transferred to third parties.

Joint owners may also grant non-exclusive licences to third parties, provided that no sublicensing rights are included. This is subject to two cumulative conditions: (i) all other joint owners must be informed in writing at least 45 days in advance, and (ii) the licence must be offered under fair and reasonable financial conditions.

The assignment or transfer of ownership of results is permitted, as long as it remains consistent with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Any transfer must include the full set of associated rights and responsibilities. Other consortium partners must be notified at least 45 days prior to the transfer and may raise objections within 30 days if the proposed change would adversely affect their access rights.

3.1.2 Access Rights

Access rights are a core mechanism for ensuring smooth cooperation among partners and for enabling the effective use and exploitation of project outputs. To this end, each partner grants the necessary rights of access to its background intellectual property as well as to the results generated during the project, to the extent required for the implementation of tasks and for the subsequent exploitation of results by other partners.

In accordance with Article 16 of the GA, the granting authority is entitled to use non-confidential information related to the action, together with materials and documentation provided by the beneficiaries, for purposes of policy support, communication, dissemination, and public outreach. This right applies both during the lifetime of the project and after its completion.

The CA further specifies tailored access-right provisions for software-based results. As a general rule, partners are entitled to access and use the object code and application programming interfaces (APIs) of project software insofar as this is necessary to exploit their own results. These rights include the ability to reproduce, distribute, and integrate the software into proprietary products or services, as well as to grant end-user sublicences for standard operation, maintenance, and interoperability, in compliance with applicable EU legal requirements.

Where access to source code is required for effective exploitation, partners may also be granted rights to inspect, modify, and adapt the source code for research, development, or productisation purposes. However, the sublicensing of source code is strictly limited to defined use cases, such as maintenance or technical support activities, and any broader or onward sublicensing is expressly excluded.

3.2 iDriving IPR Management Strategy

iDriving's IPR Management Strategy is designed as a practical, partner-oriented framework that supports innovation while safeguarding the interests of all consortium members. As the project progresses toward system integration, validation, and exploitation, IP management shifts from a theoretical exercise to an operational process embedded in day-to-day technical and strategic decisions.

Rather than treating IP protection as an isolated legal task, iDriving adopts a lifecycle-based approach in which intellectual assets are identified early, managed transparently, and aligned with each partner's exploitation ambitions. This ensures

that results can be shared within the consortium, protected when necessary, and ultimately used to generate impact beyond the project.

In line with the project's Description of Action, the iDriving IP Strategy unfolds through five distinct stages:

3.2.1 Identification and Analysis of Project Intellectual Assets

IP management in iDriving begins at the point of creation. The iDriving project brings together a wide range of intellectual assets that are developed, integrated, and validated throughout the project lifecycle. These assets are identified and analysed at an early stage to ensure clarity of ownership, appropriate protection, and controlled use within the consortium, while aligning IP management with project objectives and the commercialisation roadmap. An inventory of all software, algorithms, models, system components, and technical know-how is compiled.

Assets span multiple layers, including:

- **Foundational infrastructure:** data exchange and interoperability solutions enabling secure communication between vehicles, roadside infrastructure, UAVs, sensors, and external services.
- **Monitoring and analytics tools:** AI-driven solutions for traffic monitoring, behavioural analysis, infrastructure assessment, incident detection, and environmental hazard identification.
- **Aerial and autonomous systems:** UAV platforms, mission planning software, and data acquisition workflows for inspection, maintenance, and incident management.
- **Prediction, optimisation, and learning:** weather forecasting tools, AI-based alerting systems, risk assessment methods, and maintenance optimisation components.
- **Decision-making and user interfaces:** Digital Twin components, 3D visualisation, simulation tools, mobile and in-vehicle applications, and control centre interfaces.

Once an asset is identified, its origin and contributors are reviewed to determine ownership. Single-partner results have straightforward ownership, while joint results are documented in accordance with the GA and CA. All identified assets are listed in the iDriving IPR Registry (see Annex 2), which tracks foreground and background IP (Annex 1 CA), ownership, development stage, relevant work packages and tasks, protection mechanisms, access rights, and intended beneficiaries. The Registry is periodically reviewed and updated, with a planned re-evaluation to capture newly discovered assets and emerging synergies.

3.2.2 IP Operations

Building on the existing IPR Registry, this phase will introduce more systematic monitoring of asset evolution, including the identification of protection triggers, licensing needs, and access-right decisions. Once implemented, partners will use

this framework to receive early indications when legal actions, such as patent filings or joint-ownership arrangements, may be required. The objective is to embed IP awareness into routine project activities and to ensure that jointly developed results are managed proactively, reducing the risk of premature disclosure or missed protection opportunities.

3.2.3 Application of IP Protection and Exploitation Measures

This stage focuses on the implementation of the IP Strategy. Partners assess each asset based on maturity, strategic relevance, market potential, and exploitation plans. Depending on these factors, assets may be:

- Formally protected through patents, design rights, trademarks, or other mechanisms;
- Maintained as confidential know-how or trade secrets;
- Openly disseminated, for example through publications or open-source releases, where aligned with project objectives.

Licensing and access arrangements are carefully managed to enable use within the project, integration into technical systems, and compatibility with potential commercialization paths while safeguarding each partner's legitimate interests.

3.2.4 IP Risk Management

iDriving operates within a highly collaborative environment that brings together partners with diverse technical expertise, commercial ambitions, and organisational constraints. This diversity creates strong added value, enabling pooled knowledge, shared development efforts, and more efficient routes to market. At the same time, it increases the complexity of intellectual property (IP) management and introduces specific risks. These include uncertainty around the ownership of jointly generated results, delays in securing legal protection for inventions or brands, unintended leakage of confidential know-how, and disputes over licensing conditions or revenue allocation. Without careful coordination, such risks could undermine the long-term exploitation of project outcomes.

To mitigate these challenges, iDriving applies a combination of established governance practices and forward-looking mechanisms that evolve alongside the maturity of project results. A central element of the current approach is the IPR Registry, which functions as a living management tool. Partners are responsible for regularly updating the Registry to reflect the status and development of their assets, including background IP, newly created results, and planned protection actions. This continuous oversight supports early identification of patentable inventions, clarifies ownership positions, and helps prevent missed filing deadlines or conflicting claims.

Looking ahead, the project foresees the introduction of additional instruments to address more complex collaborative outputs. In cases where results are developed jointly by multiple partners, Joint Ownership Agreements (JOAs) will be

established. These agreements will formalise ownership proportions, set out conditions for internal use and external licensing, and define mechanisms for revenue sharing. While JOAs have not yet been executed, their inclusion in the project framework ensures that clear, agreed procedures are ready to be implemented as soon as jointly developed assets arise, thereby safeguarding the future exploitation of iDriving results both during and beyond the project lifecycle. Similarly, iDriving plans to prioritise the early identification of results with commercial potential. As work progresses, technical teams, together with LIF, will assess which outputs may require patents, utility models, trademarks, or design protection. Once identified, these results will be channelled into a support process involving legal experts to ensure filings are initiated before disclosure, thus preventing loss of rights.

In parallel, measures to safeguard confidentiality, especially trade secrets, will be strengthened. Although the Registry and internal access rules already provide a layer of control, additional mechanisms such as secure document repositories, mandatory non-disclosure agreements, clear internal procedures for handling sensitive information, and periodic audits will help prevent unauthorized disclosure and ensure compliance with trade-secret requirements. Guidance for partners on proper procedures for managing confidential information will also be developed as part of this evolving framework.

3.2.5 IP Positioning

In the final stage, the IP Strategy undergoes critical evaluation, taking into account the competitive landscape and potential market adoption of iDriving tools. Refinements are made as necessary to mitigate IP-related risks, enhance scalability, and ensure that project results remain transferable and exploitable post-project. This stage consolidates exploitation planning, ensuring that IP assets can generate long-term impact through commercial products, services, follow-up research, or policy uptake.

3.2.6 Foreground within iDriving

The foreground within iDriving is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 - Foreground within iDriving

Foreground Description	Development Stage	Main contributing partners
Tekniker Dataspace Connector	In Progress	TEKNIKER
AI-Optimized Maintenance through Digital Twin	In Progress	TEKNIKER
Anomaly Driving Behavior Detector	In Progress	TEKNIKER
Signal control	In Progress	MBL/TUC

Route guidance	In Progress	MBL/TUC
Mobile Application	In Progress	SIMAVI
In-vehicle application Tool	In Progress	SIMAVI
Digital Twin based control center	In Progress	SIMAVI
UAV Surveillance system	In Progress	ACCELI
UAV-based Path Planning for Coverage Operations	In Progress	CERTH
UAV-based Path Planning for Fast Inspection of Scattered regions	In Progress	CERTH
Seat Belt and Cell Phone Detection Tool	In Progress	CERTH
License Plate Detection Tool	In Progress	CERTH
Helmet Detection Tool	In Progress	CERTH
Fallen Tree and Rockslide Detection Tool	In Progress	CERTH
Crashed Vehicle Detection Tool	In Progress	CERTH
Pothole detection and severity assessment	In Progress	CERTH
3D SMART	In Progress	CERTH
Weather Prediction Tool using WRF and Data Assimilation	In Progress	DREVEN
AI-Based Real-Time and Forecast Weather Alert System	In Progress	DREVEN
Dynamic Monitoring Tool	In Progress	UNI.EIFFEL
Tool SUMO	In Progress	UNI.EIFFEL
Tool CARLA	In Progress	UNI.EIFFEL

3.2.7 IP Protection

While the first iteration of the IPR Strategy looks into copyright, trademark and trade secrets, it is also worth noting the protection under utility models and designs.

3.2.7.1 Utility Model

Utility models are intellectual property rights that confer exclusive control over a technical invention in return for public disclosure, offering a form of protection that is generally faster and less demanding than patents.⁵ They typically require novelty and industrial applicability but impose a lower threshold for inventive step, which makes them particularly well suited to incremental technical improvements, early prototypes, or adaptations of existing technologies that may arise during the iDriving project. Unlike patents, utility models are granted solely at national level, as no unified EU-wide registration system exists.

Efforts to introduce harmonised utility model protection across the European Union were undertaken by the European Commission in the late 1990s, including proposals issued in 1997 and revised in 1999.⁶ However, these initiatives were discontinued in 2006 due to the absence of consensus among Member States. Consequently, utility model protection remains available only in jurisdictions whose national legislation provides for this form of right, resulting in varying scopes and conditions of protection across Europe.

An EU-level study published in 2015 examined the economic impact of utility model regimes in selected Member States and found that such rights are predominantly used to protect minor or incremental inventions.⁷ The study highlights that utility models are particularly attractive to SMEs and individual innovators because they offer a relatively quick and cost-efficient route to securing exclusive rights. At the same time, it notes certain limitations, including reduced legal certainty compared to patents and inconsistent effectiveness depending on national legal frameworks.

Despite their national character, utility models benefit from EU enforcement mechanisms. In particular, Directive 2004/48/EC on the enforcement of intellectual property rights applies to national utility models, ensuring that rights holders have access to harmonised remedies in cases of infringement.⁸

Within the context of iDriving, utility models may represent a valuable protection option for technical subsystems, algorithms, or hardware-related refinements that require rapid safeguarding but may not yet satisfy the full patentability criteria. As

⁵ European Commission, “Utility models,” Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/strategy/intellectual-property/patent-protection-eu/utility-models_en.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ European Commission, Study on the economic impact of the utility model legislation in selected Member States, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2015, ISBN 9789279464775.

⁸ European Parliament and Council, “Directive 2004/48/EC of 29 April 2004 on the enforcement of intellectual property rights,” Official Journal of the European Union, L195, pp. 16–25, 2004.

part of the broader IP strategy, utility models offer a flexible and timely instrument to protect foreground results at an intermediate level of maturity, supporting early-stage exploitation and reducing the risk of competing filings by third parties.

3.2.7.2 Designs

Design rights protect the appearance of a product rather than its technical function. Under EU law, design protection was originally established by Regulation (EC) No 6/2002, which recognises a design as the visual appearance of a product or a part of it, covering elements such as lines, contours, colours and shapes among others. The regulation provides two forms of protection: Registered Community Designs (RCDs), offering long-term, renewable rights, and Unregistered Community Designs (UCDs), which arise automatically upon first public disclosure and give shorter-term protection against deliberate copying.⁹

The 2024 EU amending regulation (Regulation (EU) No 2024/2822) expanded the earlier definitions of design and product, now explicitly covering a wider range of digital and graphical elements, including non-physical visual outputs, graphical user interfaces, icons, visual layouts, and other software-related visual outputs.¹⁰ This is particularly relevant to iDriving, where design rights may protect dashboards, user interfaces, interactive components, and other digital visualisations without requiring physical embodiment, ensuring that the project's innovations remain both distinctive and safeguarded against unauthorised use.

International protection is available through WIPO's Hague System, which allows a single application in one language and with one set of fees to cover multiple jurisdictions.¹¹ The system enables centralised management of renewals, ownership changes, and updates to designs, and includes deferred publication to strategically delay disclosure until iDriving tools or interfaces are ready for deployment or integrated with other project outputs.¹²

⁹ Council Regulation (EC) No 6/2002 of 12 December 2001 on Community designs, OJ L 3, 5.1.2002, pp. 1–24.

¹⁰ Regulation (EU) 2024/2822 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 November 2024 amending Regulation (EC) No 6/2002 on Community designs, OJ L 330, 29.11.2024, pp. 1–12.

¹¹ WIPO, "Hague System for the International Registration of Industrial Designs," World Intellectual Property Organization, Geneva. [Online]. Available: <https://www.wipo.int/hague/en/>.

¹² Ibid.

4 Annex

4.1 Annex 1. iDriving DMP Questionnaire Template

iDriving Data Management Plan Questionnaire

T1.4 Data and IPR Management

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Version	Author	Date	Description
0.1	LIF	29.08.2024	Template

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

I. General File Information

1. What is this questionnaire for?

The iDriving Data Management Plan (DMP) questionnaire consolidates information about data processing and privacy practices within the consortium, aiding in the drafting of the DMP. The creation of a DMP is crucial for the iDriving project to provide guidance to the whole consortium how to handle the data collected, generated and administered throughout the lifetime of the project and to provide a basis for strategic decision-making in terms of exploitation and sustainability of the project's results. The mapping of information related to data processing will further aid legal and ethical partners in their tasks to ensure comprehensive legal and ethical compliance.

2. General Instructions

Deadline for submission: 30/09/2024

Address to: iDriving@netlaw.bg

The current questionnaire is divided into 9 sections, of which we would strongly advise you that the Section **Ethical and data protection aspects** is answered in cooperation with your organisation's Data Protection Officer (DPO). To ease the process, we have included a **Glossary: Definitions in the Context of Data Management** with some of the terms used in the end of the document, while cross-references are provided throughout the questionnaire itself.

3. Instructions in steps

1) Step One: Identify and Document Your Data.

- ✓ Identify All Data Types that you will collect, process, or generate throughout the project (e.g., personal data, survey responses).
Attention: For each data category/data type (these two terms are used synonymously), please provide a **separate answer** to the questions. For example, if you are going to process personal data and specific operational data to develop datasets, you are managing two different data categories and you need to answer the below questions for

each of the two data categories. If in doubt about the specific data category, please, refer to the not extensive list of iDriving LIF identified.

If a particular dataset falls into two or more categories simultaneously, provide answers for each relevant category and indicate the overlap between the categories.

If you identify an additional data category which is not mentioned in the list, please add it in the end, in the space left for it.

- ✓ Source of Data: Identify where each type of data will come from (e.g., surveys, sensors).
- #### 2) Step Two: Handle and Secure Your Data.
- To map the practices in each organisation relevant to this step, please fill in the questions in the Section **Data Security**
- ✓ During the Project: Store data securely and back it up regularly.
 - ✓ Security Measures: Identify and implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect data privacy and security (e.g., encryption, access controls).
- #### 3) Step Three: Make Data Findable, Accessible, and Interoperable.
- There are dedicated sections in this questionnaire to inquire on the extent to which the FAIR principles¹ are currently implemented in the project.
- ✓ Findable: Use unique persistent identifiers and clear file naming conventions. Provide relevant metadata and search keywords.
 - ✓ Accessible: Explain how data will be made accessible (e.g., in a repository) and list any tools needed for access. Specify any access restrictions.
 - ✓ Interoperable: Follow relevant data and metadata standards to ensure compatibility with other systems.
- #### 4) Step Four: Ensure Data Reusability and Compliance.
- ✓ Reusability: Specify if and how the data can be reused, under what licenses, and identify the

¹ See more information on the FAIR principles at the following links: <https://www.go-fair.org/>; <https://www.howtofair.dk/>

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

- potential users. State when the data will be available for reuse and any embargo periods.
- ✓ Compliance: Ensure compliance with GDPR and other relevant regulations. Obtain necessary consent for data administration if collected on this ground.

5) Step Five: Allocation of Resources.

- ✓ Detail the financial, human, and technical resources allocated and/or needed for data management. Include costs for making data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable).

Figure 1 – Five-step process of data management

4. Next Steps: Regular Updates to the file

To ensure effective and up-to-date data management practices throughout the iDriving project, this Data Questionnaire must be reviewed and updated every six months. LIF will be responsible for coordinating the biannual updates.

Each partner must review their sections of the DMP and update the information as needed, documenting any changes in data collection, processing, storage, sharing, and security practices. Partners must also provide updates on new data types, datasets, methodologies, and any changes in data management policies or procedures.

LIF will compile all submitted updates and review them for completeness and accuracy, addressing any discrepancies or missing information by coordinating with the respective partners.

If any partner has questions or needs assistance with the Data Questionnaire update process, they can contact LIF directly.

LIF will provide support and answer any questions related to the updates. Partners are encouraged to reach out if they need help understanding the requirements or completing their updates. For assistance, partners can contact LIF via email: iDriving@netlaw.bg.

II. Data collection tables

1. General information

This section is designed to ensure that all aspects of data handling, from production to storage, are systematically addressed to comply with relevant regulations and best practices.

GENERAL INFORMATION	
Partner	[insert here the name of your organisation]
Team	[insert here the name representative(s) responsible for completing this document"]
<i>Glossary: Definitions in the Context of Data Management</i> [data; collection of data; data generation; data processing; reusable data; unusable data; data security; data storage]	
What type of data will you produce, generate or collect during the Project? (<i>Deliverables are not included in this question</i>)	
Will you re-use any data?	
What is the origin of the data? (<i>Please, make sure to fill in information for every data type.</i>)	
What purpose does the collection/ generation/ production of data serve for the achievement of the objectives of the project (for each data type)?	
If in the questions above you have answered that there will be re-use of data, then what will you re-use it for within the project?	
How will you collect and process the data? In what formats and what is the expected size?	
How will you trace the collected data? (<i>For example, how do you trace the provenance of the data collected? Or other metadata you maintain about the collected data</i>)	

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

Will the process of data generation be reproducible? What would happen if collected data got lost or became unusable later?	
Are there tools or software needed to create/process/visualize the data?	
Does your institution have data management guidelines, any data protection and data security policy that you will follow? What are they? <i>(Please, do include information for policies on both personal and non-personal data, to the extent existent, including any national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures that you are bound to follow.)</i>	
Do you have any storage and backup strategy for the described data categories?	
Is there a third party (outside the project) that might benefit from obtaining the data collected, generated or produced by your organisation throughout the project and what is the expected utility?	

2. Making data findable

This section is designed to ensure that data generated, collected, or produced during the iDriving project is easily findable, accessible, and reusable. It focuses on assigning identifiers, naming conventions, and metadata standards to enhance data discoverability and interoperability.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE	
<i>Glossary: Definitions in the Context of Data Management</i> [digital object identifiers; metadata; version numbers]	
What project and data identifiers will be assigned?	

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

What standards will be used for documentation and provision of persistent data identifiers (e.g., DOIs)?	
What directory and file naming convention will be used?	
Will you provide clear version numbers?	
Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for discovery and re-use?	
What metadata will be created? How? <i>(Please, do include information on automated processes as well, if such are used.)</i>	
What standards will you for the integration of metadata?	
Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	

3. Making data accessible

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is accessible to authorized users while complying with relevant regulations and best practices. It focuses on the processes and methods for making data available, managing access, and ensuring data usability and security.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE	
<i>Glossary: Definitions in the Context of Data Management</i> [openly shareable data; accessible data; data repositories; access process; licensed data]	
Which data produced and/or used in the project will be available openly?	
How will the data be accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?	
Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited?	
Have you explored what the necessary arrangements of depositing data in a trusted	

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

repository would involve? Please, elaborate here.	
What methods or software tools will be needed to access the data?	
Will there be any restrictions on data access? If yes, please elaborate on the reasoning behind the impossibility to provide open access. Clearly separate legal/ contractual restrictions from intentional restrictions (e.g. overriding legitimate interest of the data holder).	
What information needs to be retained for the data to be read and interpreted in the project and in the future?	
How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?	
Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0? Will it contain information to enable the user to access the data?	
Who will sustain and provide oversight on the correct execution of the access process (e.g., PI, student, lab, University, funder)?	
How will you handle requests for data access?	
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be verified?	

4. Making data interoperable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is interoperable with other datasets and systems. It focuses on the use of standards, vocabularies, and methodologies to facilitate data integration, sharing, and reuse across different platforms and disciplines.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

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Glossary: Definitions in the Context of Data Management [standard vocabularies; interoperable data]	
Will you follow any data and metadata vocabulary standards or methodologies to facilitate interoperability? If so, please describe each of them.	
Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types?	
If you must create project specific vocabulary and/or ontology, will you openly publish them and allow their reusing, refining and extension?	
Will the data generated or collected throughout the project be made available in a machine-readable format for further reuse?	

5. Making data re-usable

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is reusable by other researchers, stakeholders, and the public. It focuses on the conditions and processes for making data reusable, including licensing, audience, and restrictions.

MAKING DATA RE-USABLE	
Glossary: Definitions in the Context of Data Management [embargo periods]	
Will you permit any data to be re-used? Please distinguish which data types will be re-usable and/or openly shareable.	
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?	
Will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse (e.g. readme files with methodology, codebooks, etc.)?	
What are the potential groups that would be interested in re-using your data? (think of both now and after the end of the project)	

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iDriving DMP Questionnaire

Are there any restrictions on who can re-use the data, for what purpose and for how long?	
When will the data be made available for re-use? Are there any embargo periods to uphold data?	
For what period will data remain re-usable?	
Will the data be licensed for re-use? If yes, could you refer to the licensing terms described when publishing/ sharing the data or the license assigned (e.g. a CC0)?	

6. Data Security

This section is designed to ensure that data produced, generated, or collected during the iDriving project is securely managed and protected. It focuses on identifying risks, implementing security measures, and ensuring data preservation and compliance with relevant regulations.

DATA SECURITY	
Glossary: Definitions in the Context of Data Management [risk assessment; data breach]	
What are the major risks to the security of your data?	
Have you prepared a formal risk assessment addressing each of the major risks to data security and how you will mitigate them?	
What technical (e.g. encryption; passwords, etc.) and organisational (e.g. office premises accessed with key/PIN; CCTV installed, need-to-know principle for personnel, etc.) measures have been enforced in your organisation for ensuring data security?	
Will any of the data produced/ collected throughout the project be encrypted? What encryption methods will be used?	
Do you foresee any additional measures to be required throughout the project implementation to ensure secure data storage?	

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

What, if any, data recovery protocols have you developed?	
Have you implemented or outlined any procedures to follow in the case of a data breach (personal or non-personal one)? If so, what are they?	
Do you intend any of the data or categories of data to be preserved long-term? How long should it be retained (e.g., 3-5 years, 10-20 years, permanently)?	
Where will such data be maintained? Are there data archives that are appropriate for your data (subject-based or institutional)?	
Who decides what data or what categories of data will be kept and for how long and on what basis?	
Who will maintain the data for the long term?	
There are some requirements on retention of personal data ensuing from the GDPR. What protocol(s) will you put in place to ensure you delete personal data that is no longer required to be stored?	
Will any third party be involved in or responsible for the management or storage of data? If so, who will it be and what data category or data type will each third-party store?	

7. Ethical and data protection aspects

This section is designed to ensure that the iDriving project adheres to ethical standards and data protection regulations when collecting, generating, or processing personal, sensitive, and criminal conviction data. It focuses on identifying the types of data involved, obtaining necessary consents, ensuring compliance with GDPR, and implementing measures to protect data subjects.

ETHICAL AND DATA PROTECTION ASPECTS

To be completed by your Legal department / Data protection officer

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iDriving DMP Questionnaire

Glossary: Definitions in the Context of Data Management [personal data; data minimisation; web scraping; big data; profiling; pseudonymisation; anonymisation; confidentiality; data transfer]	
<p>Will you or do you intend to collect, generate or process any of these data categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data; • Data on criminal convictions and offences; • Operational data for LEAs; • Sensitive information related to critical infrastructure protection; • Classified information on national and/or international grounds; • Commercial confidential information (e.g. company secret). <p>Please answer as comprehensively as possible.</p>	
<p>If any of the categories of non-personal, but protected data will be handled, please elaborate on the process of obtaining and administering any such data, the grounds they were received on, the terms of usage and how they should be handled after the end of the project.</p>	
<p>If you intend to process personal data, as defined by the GDPR, which of the six Art. 6 bases will you rely on?</p>	
<p>Will you ensure the obtaining of the explicit consent of data subjects for the collection and administration of their personal data (incl. data preservation and sharing, if applicable)? If not, please elaborate.</p>	

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

If you intend to process sensitive personal data as defined by the GDPR, which of the ten Art. 9 bases will you rely on?	
If the data is about criminal convictions and offences, as defined by the GDPR, how do you plan to comply with Art. 10?	
Will any of the data subjects be children or individuals belonging to other vulnerable groups (i.e. groups that are commonly put in an unequal position based on a common characteristic)?	
How will you protect the identity of the project participants?	
Will you share personal data with consortium partners and under what terms/ scope? Which partner needs your data to perform his/her task?	
Will you engage in big data processing?	
Does data processing within your tasks lead to personal profiling? Could the project's results be exploited for the purposes of profiling/ social scoring or similar practices?	
Could the data processing have any adverse effects on the data subjects in the case personal data is processed and administered?	
Will you engage in web scraping?	
Will there be an engagement with entities outside of the EU either for the import, or for the export of personal data (data transfer) throughout the project's duration? If	

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

yes, please specify for which data categories, with which entities, where they have their main establishment and other details that might be available to you.	
Do you plan to use pseudonymisation and/or anonymisation techniques for any data category? If so, how do you plan to implement this?	
Have you conducted a data minimisation review to ensure that you need all the data that you intend to process?	
Can any of the data processed be made openly shareable after applying the respective techniques for de-identification? Please elaborate in new line, if applicable, for each separate data category.	
Do you foresee any additional legal or ethical issues that might affect data sharing as envisaged within the project?	
Please provide the contacts of your organisation's DPO if one was required to be appointed under the GDPR. <i>If not applicable, please indicate so.</i>	

8. Allocation of resources

The purpose of this section is to outline and document the resources required for effective data management throughout the iDriving project. This includes financial, human, and technical resources necessary to ensure that the project data is managed in compliance with relevant regulations and standards, particularly focusing on making the data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable). This table helps in planning, budgeting, and ensuring that all necessary resources are allocated to maintain data integrity, security, and accessibility.

ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
What resources (financial, human, technical) are allocated for data	

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

management within your organisation?	
Would there be any extra costs incurring for your organisation for making the Project data FAIR? How will they be covered?	
Will there be any fee(s) associated with the storage of data in dedicated repositories? How will they be covered?	
Will you need to pay service fees for any specialist to assist with or maintain data repositories or data access?	
What costs do you anticipate incurring in time and what effort to prepare the data for sharing/preservation?	

9. Data processing overview

The purpose of this section is to ensure comprehensive documentation and transparency of data processing activities within the project. **Please, fill out the information only about the tasks you lead.**

Task	What Data will you use?	Why do you need this data?	Where do you get the data from?	Do you plan to share the data within the consortium?	Could the data be useful for parties outside the consortium? If yes, are there reasons not to share?	What measures (technical and organizational) are in place to protect the data?
T1.1						
T1.2						
T1.3						
T1.4						
T1.5						

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T2.1						
T2.2						
T2.3						
T2.4						
T2.5						
T3.1						
T3.2						
T3.3						
T3.4						
T3.5						
T4.1						
T4.2						
T4.3						
T4.4						
T4.5						
T5.1						
T5.2						
T5.3						
T5.4						
T5.5						
T6.1						
T6.2						
T6.3						
T6.4						

III. Definitions and other reference materials

1. Glossary: Definitions in the Context of Data Management

- 1. Accessible Data**
Data that is easily retrievable and usable by authorized users, ensuring that data can be found and accessed when needed, often adhering to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).²
- 2. Access process**
The access process refers to the procedures and mechanisms through which authorized individuals or systems can retrieve, view, or use data stored within an information system. The primary purpose of the access process is to ensure that data is available to authorized users while protecting it from unauthorized access, thereby maintaining data confidentiality, integrity, and availability
- 3. Anonymization**
The process of irreversibly removing personal identifiers from data so that the data subject can no longer be identified, ensuring that the data is no longer subject to data protection laws.³
- 4. Collection of Data**
The systematic gathering of data from various sources, ensuring its accuracy and completeness for further processing.
- 5. Confidentiality**
The obligation to protect personal data from unauthorized access and disclosure, ensuring that only authorized individuals can access the data.⁴
- 6. Data**
Any digital representation of acts, facts, or information and any compilation of such acts, facts, or information, including in the form of sound, visual, or audiovisual recording.⁵
- 7. Data and Metadata Vocabularies**
Standardized sets of terms and definitions used to describe data and metadata, facilitating interoperability and understanding across different systems and domains.
- 8. Data Breach**
A breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, or unauthorized disclosure of, or access to data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed.
- 9. Data Encryption**
The process of converting data into a coded format to prevent unauthorized access, ensuring that only authorized parties can decrypt and read the data.
- 10. Data Generation**
The process of creating new data through various means, such as data collection, experimentation, or simulation.
- 11. Data Governance**
The overall management of the availability, usability, integrity, and security of data used in an organization. It includes policies, procedures, and standards for data management.
- 12. Data Identifiers**
Unique markers or codes used to distinguish and reference specific data elements, ensuring accurate identification and retrieval.
- 13. Data Integrity**
The accuracy and consistency of data over its lifecycle, ensuring that data remains correct, complete, and reliable.
- 14. Data Lifecycle**
The stages through which data progresses, from creation and initial storage to the time it becomes obsolete and is deleted.
- 15. Data Management**

² See more : <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>; <https://howtofair.dk/what-is-fair/#fair-principles>

³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679; Preamble, par 26

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679; Article 5, par 1(f)

⁵ Regulation (EU) 2022/868; Art. 2, par 1

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

The comprehensive process of handling data throughout its lifecycle, including collection, storage, processing, sharing, and disposal, ensuring data quality, security, and compliance.

16. Data Management Plan (DMP)

A formal document outlining how data will be managed during and after a research project.

17. Data Minimisation

Personal data shall be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed'.⁶

18. Data Processing

Any operation or set of operations performed on personal data or sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction.⁷

19. Data Recovery

Procedures and technologies used to restore data that has been lost, corrupted, or made inaccessible, ensuring business continuity and data integrity.

20. Data Repositories

Centralized storage locations where data is collected, maintained, and managed, often used to facilitate data sharing, access, and analysis.

21. Data Security

Measures and protocols implemented to protect data from unauthorized access, alteration, disclosure, or destruction, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data.⁸

22. Data Space

An integrated set of interoperable electronic services for collecting, processing, and exchanging relevant information.

23. Data Storage

Data storage refers to the collection, retention, and management of digital data systematically and securely. It involves the use of various technologies and methodologies to store data in a way that ensures its availability, integrity, and security. The primary purpose of data storage is to preserve data for future access, analysis, and use while protecting it from loss, corruption, and unauthorized access.

24. Data Subject

A data subject is an identified or identifiable natural person to whom personal data relates. In the context of data protection laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the data subject is the individual whose personal data is being collected, held, or processed.⁹

25. Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)

Persistent identifiers used to uniquely identify digital objects, such as documents or datasets, facilitating their access and citation.

26. Embargo Periods to Uphold Data

Specific timeframes during which access to certain data is restricted to ensure compliance with legal, ethical, or contractual obligations before the data can be made publicly available or shared.

27. Interoperable Data

Data that is structured and formatted in a way that allows it to be easily integrated and used across different systems and platforms, ensuring seamless data exchange and use.¹⁰

28. Large-Scale or Big-Data Processing

The processing of vast amounts of data that require advanced methods and technologies to analyse, manage, and extract meaningful insights, often involving complex datasets from various sources.¹¹

29. Licensed Data

Data is made available under specific terms and conditions defined by a license, which dictates how the data can be used, shared, and distributed.

⁶ Regulation (EU) 2016/679; Art. 5, par. 1(c)

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2016/679; Art. 4, par 2

⁸ Regulation (EU) 2016/679; Article 5, par 1(f)

⁹ General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Article 4(1)

¹⁰ See more : <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>; <https://howtofair.dk/what-is-fair/#fair-principles>

¹¹ See resolution of the European Parliament: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52017IP0076>

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

30. Metadata

Data that provides information about other data, such as its origin, structure, and context, used to facilitate data management and retrieval.

31. Openly Sharable Data

Data that is made available to the public or specific groups without restrictions, often under open data policies to promote transparency, innovation, and reuse.

32. Personal Data

Any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person ('data subject'); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier, or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that natural person.¹²

33. Pseudonymisation

The processing of personal data in such a manner that the data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, which is kept separately and subject to technical and organizational measures to ensure non-attribution.¹³

34. Profiling

'Any form of automated processing of personal data consisting of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, in particular to analyse or predict aspects concerning that natural person's performance at work, economic situation, health, personal preferences, interests, reliability, behavior, location or movements.¹⁴

35. Protocols for Transfer of Personal Data

Established procedures for the transfer of personal data between entities, especially across borders, ensuring compliance with data protection laws.¹⁵

36. Re-usable Data

Data that can be used multiple times for various purposes, often facilitated by open data policies and standards that ensure data is available for further use and analysis.¹⁶

37. Risk Assessment

The process of identifying, evaluating, and prioritizing risks associated with data processing activities, followed by coordinated efforts to minimize, monitor, and control the probability or impact of such risks.

38. Standard Vocabularies

Agreed-upon sets of terms and definitions used to ensure consistency and clarity in data descriptions and communications.

39. Unusable Data:

Data that is corrupted, incomplete, or otherwise unsuitable for its intended use, often requiring cleaning or transformation.

40. Version Numbers

Identifiers assigned to different iterations of a dataset or document are used to track changes and ensure the use of the correct version.

41. Web-Scraping

The automated extraction of data from websites using software tools, can raise legal and ethical issues related to data ownership, privacy, and terms of service violations.

¹² Regulation (EU) 2016/679; Art. 4, par 1

¹³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679; Art. 4, par 5

¹⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679; Art. 4, par. 4

¹⁵ Regulation (EU) 2016/679; Chapter V

¹⁶ See more : <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>; <https://howtofair.dk/what-is-fair/#fair-principles>

iDriving DMP Questionnaire

2. Data Categories in iDriving

This is a non-exhaustive list of the data categories within the iDriving Project.	
Data Category	Description
Personal Data	Identification Data, Biometric Data, Contact Information, Behavioural Data
Security Data	Traffic and Safety Alerts, Risk Assessments
Technical Data	Sensor Data, Vehicle Data, Infrastructure Data
Analytical Data	AI Models and Algorithms, Data Analytics, Statistical Data
High-Value Datasets	Meteorological Data, Geospatial Data, Transportation and Mobility Data
Compliance and Legal Data	Legal Documents, Compliance Records
Interoperability and Shareability Data	Metadata, Data Standards, Data Exchange Records
User Management Data	User Profiles, Authentication Data, Access Control Logs
[If you have identified an additional data category, please insert it here]	[Please describe the newly identified data category in this section]
[If you have identified an additional data category, please insert it here]	[Please describe the newly identified data category in this section]

iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/07/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01 **Total cost:** € 4,998,733.75 **Coordinator:** Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH)

Funded by the European Union

The Project "iDriving - Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies" has received funding from the European Union's Horizon EUROPE Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101147004.

iDriving Consortium